

PROBLEMS TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN UZBEKISTAN

Dilnoza Nazarova

Student of Uz SWLU

E-mail: dilnozaumirzakovna@gmail.com
studentkajahontillari@mail.com

Phone number: +998937588833

Supervisor: Zafar Nurmatovich Abdusamadov O'zDJTU Ingliz tili 3-fakulteti dekani
f.f.f.d.,PhD

Abstract: Decisions made in setting the direction of education policy today have a wide range of impacts on the scientific, economic, political and cultural needs of the country. The early foreign language education system for children introduced in some countries of the world since the 1990s also corresponds to our country, and from 2017 to 2018 we will adopt several legal documents related to this field. was proposed.

Key words: education, system, language, scientific, political.

There are several solution these problem in our country:

Early childhood language learning

A normally developing child is able to learn any language they encounter in their environment and has the potential to communicate with others. Reducing the number of languages a child can learn from a neurological point of view is not the subject of our conversation. language can be learned. However, children's proficiency (ability) in any language varies according to their needs and circumstances in using the language. Today, many studies show that success is achieved when early childhood foreign language teaching is conducted using appropriate methods and approaches. However, such results can only be achieved through the use of language teaching methods and materials appropriate to the student's learning level. This has her two main requirements.

The student's ability to communicate and use the foreign language taught in a foreign language environment and to demonstrate the taught language in a meaningful context.

Inappropriate number of lessons per week

In a system like ours where foreign languages are taught only, the timing of opportunities for communication in the language environment and the speed at which the language is taught are extremely important. A regular and robust curriculum for 5-7 years to acquire listening, speaking, reading, writing and vocabulary acquisition skills and to be able to use all these skills academically correctly and in a foreign language is required. From this point of view, we believe that this is not enough when it comes to

offering her a week of foreign language classes in grades 2, 3 and 4. Language teaching, by its very nature, is both a written and oral means of communication and requires continuity. It is impossible for a 7-8 years old elementary school student to learn a foreign language system with only 4-5 hours of communication per week and no opportunity to use it in their own environment.

Textbooks should not be the only source of knowledge

Another serious problem in language teaching relates to the methods and teaching tools used for language teaching. Examination of textbooks used in public primary schools reveals a lack of relationships between topical constructs and lexical units, despite their rich vocabulary. In real life, when using language in any situation, every sentence that comes out of your mouth is semantically related to the sentence that came before or after it. With today's rapidly advancing technology, there is no doubt that textbooks should not be the sole source of language learning. Considering that teachers in our country use textbooks for foreign language teaching in 80% of cases, other books and additional teaching materials should be prepared with special care. I found myself in a situation where a 7-8years old who started learning a foreign language in 2nd grade found that by the end of 4th grade, he was learning in the language he claimed to be studying. For three years, last week or yesterday, I cannot explain the actions taken. Because the content of the books used in elementary school does not allow this.

Some languages are learned early

In the early stages of foreign language learning, we see the influence of the characteristics of the student's native language. Such situations, called "cross-language activities," demonstrate that there is a constant interaction between the native language that is anchored in a student's memory and the other language that they are beginning to learn. As for language learning, many aspects of language also develop slowly. Some features and aspects of the language were learned earlier, others later. Language differences can take a long time to master many things that seem easy. Without the opportunity for students to hear and use the language being used, it is impossible to develop their language learning positively and they quickly forget what they have already learned.

Don't expect miracles when learning a foreign language

All material presented in language learning should make sense and topics should be related to each other and, where appropriate, to what the child has learned in other lessons. there is. In this case, the foreign language teacher should work with other teachers teaching a particular class to plan. It also needs to consider and connect each

student's experience and life in the learning process. From this perspective, the educational process can use content-based educational models and fairy tales, songs that correspond to levels of cognitive, linguistic and social development, and activities that directly involve students. So, considering that more than half of the world's population speaks two or more languages in their daily lives, you can be confident that learning a foreign language is no miracle. In addition, you can teach your students a foreign language not only as an opportunity for success that most people cannot achieve, but also to keep up with the times.

REFERENCES

1. <https://m.daryo.uz/2019/03/11/ozbekistonda-chet-tillarini-oqitish-muammolari-ular-qanchalik-jiddiy/>
2. <https://www.etoninstitute.com/blog/top-10-benefits-of-learning-a-foreign-language>
3. <https://www.studyfrenchspanish.com/language-benefits/>

